

A Multi Encryption based on AES and RSA for Secure Message Dissemination over Vehicular Ad-Hoc Network

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Abstract- The Scope of VANET are whole for public safety and transfer of information each other For example, warning messages sent by vehicles involved in an accident enhances traffic safety by helping the approaching drivers to take proper decisions before entering the crash dangerous zone. And Information about the current transportation conditions facilitate driving by taking new routes in case of congestion, thus saving time and adjusting fuel consumption In addition to safety concerns, VANET can also support other non-safety applications that require a Quality of Service (QoS) guarantee. This paper proposed multi encryption approach for data encryption and decryption sp that Vehicle can perform secure communication. In this work implement security algorithm based on Advance Encryption standard and RSA algorithm and estimate performances.

Keywords- VANET, QoS, Security

I. INTRODUCTION

VANET research is very emerging area for researchers now days. Many issues arise when efforts are gathered towards running vehicular ad hoc networks in an attempt to provide an improvement to driver behavior, with the aim of reducing the number of Fatalities caused by automobile accidents. The main important challenges in VANET and the key challenges from the Technical perspectives are as follows:

Signal fading: Objects placed as obstacles between two communicating vehicles are one of the challenges that can affect the efficiency of VANET. these obstacles can be other vehicles or buildings distributed along roads especially in the cities Bandwidth limitations. Another key issue in the VANET is the absence of a central coordinator that

controls the communications between nodes, and which has the responsibility of managing the bandwidth and contention operation.

Connectivity: Owing to the high mobility and rapid changes of topology, which lead to a frequent fragmentation in networks, the time duration required to elongate the life of the link communication should be as long as possible. This task can be accomplished by increasing the transmission power; however, that may lead to throughput degradation. Accordingly, connectivity is considered to be an important issue in VANET, Owing to the small effective network diameter of a VANET that lead to a weak connectivity in the communication between nodes.

Security and privacy: Keeping a reasonable balance between the security and privacy is one of the main challenges in VANET. The receipt of trustworthy information from its source is Important for the receiver.

Routing protocol: Because of the high mobility of nodes and rapid changes of topology, designing an efficient routing protocol that can deliver a packet in a minimum period of time with few dropped packets is considered to be a critical challenge in VANETs.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

Y. Yang et al., [1] it is study the periods of sequences produced by the cascade connection of two Feedback shift registers (FSRs). The period of the cascade connection is the period of the longest sequences it produces. An upper bound for the period of the cascade connection of a Nonlinear feedback shift register (NFSR) into a Linear feedback shift register (LFSR) is established. In addition, the cascade connection of an n -stage maximum-length LFSR into an n -stage NFSR is called an $(n + n)$ -stage Grain-like NFSR, and it is propose two families of $(n$

+ n)stage Grain-like NFSRs such that the minimal period $2^n - 1$ is achievable for a positive integer n .

H. Zhong et al., [2] Intelligent connected vehicles are autonomous vehicles. With the increasing degree of automation of autonomous vehicles and the development of open applications in the future, the computing tasks of autonomous vehicles are becoming more and more complex. In practice, the computing resources of vehicles are limited and the processing of data is not always guaranteed to be completed in time. However, the timely processing and integrity of the data are very important for vehicles because it affects the path selection of the traveling vehicle and the passenger experience. Therefore, it is necessary to reduce latency in processing data and verify the integrity of data for vehicles. In this work, a novel message authentication scheme for multiple mobile devices in intelligent connected vehicles based on edge computing is proposed.

H. Wang et al., [3] Multiple servers collaboration technology furnishes an effective storage management platform to the service providers. The massive data, which belong to disparate providers, possesses distinct access policies for each user. Authentication applied to multiple servers architecture is recognized as a remarkable mechanism for access control and authorization of users.

R. Tiwari et al., [4] Mobile ad hoc networks (MANETs) are normal in improving road wellbeing and traffic conditions, in which security is basic. In MANETs, the authentication of the mobile access control is a vital security administration for both inter-vehicle and vehicle-roadside unit correspondences. In the mean time, vehicles additionally must be kept from the abuse of the private data and the assaults on their privacy.

T. Zhou, et al., [5] As an important cryptographic primitive in cloud computing and outsourced computing, fully homomorphic encryption (FHE) is an animated area in modern cryptography. However, the efficiency of FHE has been a bottleneck that impeding its application. According to Gentry's blueprint, bootstrapping, which is used to control the noise propagation in cipher texts, is the most

important process in FHE. However, bootstrapping is also the most expensive process that affects the scheme's efficiency. This work has made three improvements to accelerate the bootstrapping. Firstly, as hundreds of serial homomorphic additions take most of the time of bootstrapping, it is constructed the logical expression using truth table to reduce the amount of serial homomorphic additions by two-thirds and thus proposed an efficient FHE scheme with bootstrapping within 10 ms. Secondly, the most expensive parts in our bootstrapping, enhanced homomorphic constant multiplication and homomorphic addition, can be implemented in parallel, which may accelerate the bootstrapping. At last, it is proposed a set of more efficient combinations of parameters. Analysis shows that our scheme's security level is 128 bits and the correctness is improved compared with CGGI16 scheme in ASIACRYPT 2016. Experiments show that the running time of bootstrapping in this work is within 10 ms, which is only 52% of CGGI16, and is less than CGGI17 in ASIACRYPT 2017.

X. Jia, et al., [6] A (k, n) -conventional visual cryptography (VC) scheme is designed to share one secret and each participant takes one share. When some common participants are involved in multiple VC schemes for multiple secrets, each needs to take multiple shares. This procedure needs more shares, which is inconvenient. It is desirable that the collaboration between the VC schemes can allow each common participant to keep only one share. Simply merging or gluing together two traditional (k_1, n_1) and (k_2, n_2) -VC schemes, after making their pixel expansions the same, might be able to facilitate the collaboration and allow each common participant to keep only one share. But there is a security risk that when a subset of k_1 participants are from the collection of non common participants, some from scheme 1 and some from scheme 2, they can reconstruct secret 1, which is inconsistent with the intention of the original scheme. Similarly, k_2 non common participants could reconstruct secret 2. This shortcoming is inherited from the brute-force combination of traditional schemes. Y. Wang et al., [6] Due to the broadcasting property of visible light communication (VLC) channels, VLC systems are under the threat of eavesdropping and malicious attack. In this study, the authors present an

uncoordinated chaotic channel scrambling scheme to enhance the physical layer security for a multiple-input, multiple-output based VLC system. With the authors design, the legitimate receiver can self-descramble the data with the location information shared between the transceivers, and the eavesdroppers cannot retrieve the information without the secret key.

III. VANET - CHALLENGES

VANET is a wireless communication between Vehicle to Vehicle and Vehicle-to-Roadside infrastructure. VANETs have different challenges as compared with MANET. VANET has traffic, safety and user application based challenges which have some specific design requirements.

S. No.	Challenge Base	Challenge	Design Requirement
1.	Traffic Base Challenge	Highly Dynamic Vehicles Lesser Bandwidth Traffic jam, Traffic light and intersection of road (Emergency conditions)	Dynamic Topology Less flooding in network Good congestion control mechanism
2.	Safety Based Challenges	Breaching of Privacy Of Vehicles Government and authorities surveillance	User authentication and data authentication Balance in privacy and liabilities
3.	User application base challenges	Revenue Generation for funding VANET	Require flooding of information in the network

IV. PROPOSED METHODOLOGY

A. Collection of Data

The data will be collected from primary as well as secondary sources. The primary sources of data would be collected through personal observation, discussions questioner and interview with the personnel working at various levels of the organization i.e. from top to operational level officers.

The secondary data sources would be collected from books, articles published in various journals, booklets, annual reports, magazines, web sites etc.

B. Coding and Tabulation

After the interview, the information in the questioner will be edited and after editing the information, each information will be assign the number. This is known as Code Manual. After the codification of data, the data will be presented in the form of tables depending upon the type of information and requirement of the testing of hypotheses.

C. Analysis and Interpretation of data

Analysis work after tabulation is generally based on the computation of various percentages, coefficients, chi-square test etc., by applying various well defined statistical formulae. In the process of analysis, relationships or differences supporting or conflicting with original or new hypotheses should be subjected to tests of significance to determine with what validity data can be said to indicate any conclusion(s).

D. RSA

RSA is based on one important mathematical phenomenon: the difficulty of factoring large numbers. RSA is a member of the asymmetric encryption algorithms. The public and private keys are derived from a pair of large (min. 200 digits) prime numbers, P and Q . Keys are generated as follows:

1. Compute $n = pq$ and $z = (p-1)(q-1)$.
2. Randomly choose the encryption key e , such that e and z are relatively prime.

3. Choose a decryption key d , such that $ed \pmod z = 1$. In general, d is calculated with help of the Euclidean algorithm.

Key generation is now completed. The public key is defined as $\langle e, n \rangle$ and the private key as $\langle d, n \rangle$. The two prime numbers p and q are not longer needed and should be discarded. To encrypt a message m , compute $c = me \pmod n$. For decryption use $m = cd \pmod n$.

E. AES

AES is a variant of Rijndael with a fixed block size. AES ciphers use a 128-bit block and 128, 192 or 256-bit keys. The larger block size helps resist birthday attacks while the large key size prevents brute force attacks . It is efficient in both software and hardware.

The main features of AES are:

- AES does not use a Feistel network. It uses 10, 12, or 14 rounds.
- 128-bit input/output data block size
- 128, 192, and 256-bits key sizes. The key size depends on the number of rounds.
- AES uses one S-box which takes in 8 bits and outputs 8 bits.

V. RESULT

Fig 1: Flow chart of Security Model

Fig 2: Simulation of Key Generation by RSA Algorithm

Fig 3: Graph of Original key Vs Cipher key

Figure 4: Simulation of VANET.(100meter x 100meter area)

(b) VANET simulation 500 meter X 500 Meter

(c) VANET simulation 100 meter X 100 Meter

Figure 4: Simulation of VANET

Table 1: Simulation Parameter

Simulator	MATLAB 8.0.3.532
Simulation time	20(s)
MAC layer protocol	802.11
Number of mobile nodes	2
Topology	Mesh
Traffic loading speed	1 CBR packet/s
Routing protocol	AODV
Maximum bandwidth	27 mbps
Traffic	Constant bit rate
Maximum speed	2-10m/s
Packet size	512 bytes
Simulation area	100 m x 100m

Table 2: Comparative execution time (in seconds) and buffer size of encryption algorithms

Input data(bytes)	Method	Computation Time(seconds)		Buffer Size (Bytes)
		Encryption	Decryption	
128	DES	0.5416	0.2007	4096
	AES	0.0424	0.063	6232
	RSA	0.0771	0.0735	448
256	DES	0.8795	0.5232	4324
	AES	0.0303	0.0425	6648
	RSA	0.1474	0.1427	904
512	DES	1.3868	1.1493	6580
	AES	0.0254	0.0474	7480
	RSA	0.3117	0.3451	1736

Table 3: Comparative result analysis of all algorithms with proposed method

Input Size(bytes)	Method	Simulation Time(seconds)		Throughput	
		Encryption	Decryption	(Encryption)	(Decryption)
512	DES	2.8079	1.8732	319.1	478.3
512	AES	0.0981	0.1531	9133.5	5852.4
512	RSA	0.5362	0.5613	1671.1	1596.3
512	Proposed Method	0.1146	0.1144	7818.5	7859.7

Figure 5: Comparative Throughput analyses of all algorithms with proposed method

After seen simulation graph and result it is clear that proposed method gives better result than existing approaches.

VI. CONCLUSION

In this paper, security algorithm for VANETs is studied and implemented multi encryption algorithm. Choosing the correct security algorithm providing with appropriate simulation will improve the performance security algorithm in VANETs. MATLAB 8.3 software is using to simulate proposed approach. Simulated results shows that the proposed algorithm gives better performance than previous hybrid methods in terms of simulation time, buffer size, security level etc.

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